

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF SUPERADOBE WITH VARYING CEMENT PERCENTAGES

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ABSTRACT

This explorative study characterizes three types of superadobe mixtures to assess their compliance with compressive strength as specified in the ESR-4126 Evaluation Report, issued by the ICC. The soil materials used were: *mogolla serpentina*, *mogolla caliza* and a mix of 80% *mogolla caliza* and 20% *consumo* soil. For each soil, three mixes with varying cement volumetric proportions (7, 10, 13) were evaluated. Though this explorative study is the first step towards developing standardized mixes in Puerto Rico, further studies should be performed to confirm these mixes are in compliance with the other criteria specified in the report.

Keywords

Superadobe; compressive strength; accessible housing

INTRODUCTION

Puerto Rico has been undergoing a housing crisis for nearly two decades (Hinojosa & Meléndez, 2018). The situation has been aggravated by humanitarian crises triggered by natural events such as Hurricane María in 2017, and the earthquake swarms of 2020. The occurrence of these events had catastrophic consequences on housing structures on the island. Hurricane María resulted in the damage of almost 23% of housing units on the island, according to reports by FEMA. Though it is important to note that only *formal* (or permitted) homes are eligible to receive compensation for damages, which hinders recuperation efforts given the high number of *informal* (or unpermitted) housing on the island. The United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development, defines informal housing settlements as: "... residential areas where 1) inhabitants have no security of tenure vis-à-vis the land or dwellings they inhabit, with modalities ranging from squatting to informal rental housing, 2) the neighborhoods usually lack, or are cut off from, basic services and city infrastructure and 3) the housing may not comply with current planning and building regulations, and is often situated in geographically and environmentally hazardous areas" (United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Development, 2016). No statistic exists on the number of informal housings in PR, though some conservative estimates range around 700,000 homes (Hinojosa & Meléndez, 2018). Informal homes affected by the hurricane or earthquakes are not eligible for compensation from FEMA, complicating rebuilding efforts for people who are already in a precarious situation. For people in this situation rebuilding with conventional materials like wood and concrete may not be a viable option given the high costs of these materials. However, other materials of lesser cost present a viable opportunity for reconstruction. Earth is a nonconventional material that can met these criteria.

Earthen construction techniques are of lesser cost than conventional materials, however techniques can vary greatly depending on soil type and local weather conditions. Therefore, it is crucial to properly characterize soil to determine its material properties and compliance with building codes, when and where they are applicable. In Puerto Rico, one of the most common earthen construction techniques is superadobe or earthbag building. Currently, there are efforts to obtain construction permits and codify this material in the archipelago. This study is aimed at evaluating common superadobe mixes on the island and (1) determine which of these mixes is able to meet metrics established by the ICC and (2) begin to develop a replicable characterization technique that can be used in future projects.

Superadobe is a construction technique that employs a soil mix in bags that are then horizontally stacked above one another. The soil in the bags undergoes a dual, chemical and mechanical stabilization, as a binder such as cement is typically combined with the soil material which is then mechanically stabilized through compaction (Canadell, Blanco, & Cavalaro, 2016). During mechanical compaction- which is done by hand using a tamper- the bags serve as formwork, which hold the material in place. Between courses of bags, barbed wire is placed to increase friction between the bags and enhance the walls' shear resistance (Figure 1). Materials for superadobe construction are significantly less expensive than conventional materials, since the main component is soil which can be sourced at the construction site or bought for a very low price from a local quarry, usually located some 50 kilometers from the site. In the context of resiliency, superadobe housing is very robust and resilient to extreme climatic conditions (or to natural disasters). It is notably used as emergency shelters or housing in the aftermath of earthquakes and hurricanes. On the island, several superadobe structures have been built, and were able to withstand both Hurricane María and 2020 Earthquakes without any damages to the structures (Lebron, 2020).

Figure 1: Parts of the construction of a superadobe dome. Clockwise: (a) workers filling polypropylene bags; (b) skylight of dome; (c) workers finishing final courses of a dome; (d) a worker laying the barbed wire between courses.

Nonetheless, superadobe is still in the process of widespread standardization and code acceptance. The biggest efforts towards code approval have been led by the California Institute of Earth Art and Architecture (Cal-Earth). This organization was founded by the architect who pioneered the superadobe

construction method, Nadir Khalil, and is focused on education, development and research in earth architecture (Khalili & Vittore, 1998). Cal-Earth has constructed several superadobe structures that have been approved by building officials in the state of California. The work undertaken by Cal-Earth to lay the groundwork for widespread acceptance and permitting has been long and complex, spanning over three decades. Most recently, these efforts have led to an evaluation led by the International Code Council Evaluation Service (ICC-ES) to corroborate compliance of Cal-Earth superadobe materials with the 2018 International Residential Code. The final report summarizes the requirements for all material components of superadobe (soil mix, bags and barbed wire), and found them to be in compliance with the 2018 IRC (International Code Council Evaluation Service, 2020). The report can also serve as a guide for the evaluation of other material requirements and of other superadobe mixes. This current study aims to explore superadobe mixes in Puerto Rico and their capabilities to comply with code requirements, to further advance the process of standardization and permitting of superadobe structures on the island.

Superadobe constructions in Puerto Rico typically use a soil material locally referred to as *mogolla*. This term describes the material discarded at quarries during the production of gravel. It encompasses everything that is less than 3 inches. Due to the large variability of soils on the island, there is great variability between *mogollas* coming from different quarries. For this study, two types of *mogolla* were used for the elaboration of soil mixes: *mogolla Serpentina* and *mogolla Caliza*. *Serpentina* is weathered serpentine derived from serpentinite rocks, while *Caliza* is limestone (Figures 2a & 2b). *Mogolla* soils used have a USCS classification of SM (silty sands, sand-silt mixtures) (Badía, 2020). A third mix was made incorporating 20% by volume of clayey soils found at a superadobe construction site in the Plenitud PR farm. USCS classification is yet to be determined for this soil.

(a) Particle size distribution curve for *mogolla Srrpentina*.

(b) Particle size distribution curve for *mogolla Caliza*

Figure 2: Particle size distribution curves for *mogolla* soils used (Badía, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The three types of soil mixes consisted of a soil base of: *Mogolla Serpentina* from San German (S), *Mogolla Caliza* from Cabo Rojo (Ca), and *Mogolla Caliza* with 20% clayey soil from Las Marias by volume (CaB). For each soil type, thirty cylinders were prepared; 10 corresponding to each proportion of cement added by volume (7%, 10%, 13%). The proportions of cement were determined from the

experience of local builders. Cement used was hydraulic type GU. Samples were identified in accordance with their base soil mix, cement proportion and number. For example, a cylinder of *serpentina* with 7% is identified as S7%#. In order to test compressive strength, cylinders molds used were in accordance with ASTM c67 Section 7. These cylinders were of 4-in diameter and 8-in height.

Figure 3: Assembly for cylinder sample preparation.

The process of mix preparation was designed to replicate field conditions as closely as possible so results would reflect real working conditions. The soil-cement mix was elaborated in large batches using the shovel method. Following the established volumetric proportions, soil and cement were mixed. During this process water was added in small amounts to enhance bonding between cement and soil and better mix manageability. The amounts of water necessary were determined by empirical tests- such as the ball test- and an experienced builder's expertise. Once the mix was found adequate, it was tamped in cylinders using an assembly that facilitated tamping (Figure 3). Samples were left to cure in a roofed, open space where they were partially exposed to natural elements like sun and rain. They were left to cure within the plastic mould cylinders for 21 days, after this the moulds were removed and the specimens were left to cure for an additional week in the same conditions.

Testing was performed at the Victor E. Rivera Associates, L.L.C. Geotechnical Engineers & Concrete Testing Laboratories in Ponce, PR. Compressive strength tests were carried out on a Universal Testing Machine (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Cylinder samples awaiting testing at the laboratory.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results from testing were grouped in accordance with their mix ID. For each set of results, standard deviation was calculated. A graph was generated for comparison between different cement percentages for each soil type. The minimum acceptable average value for compressive strength is 300 psi and none less than 250 psi, in accordance with Table 2 of the ICC-ESR 4126. This is the minimum compressive strength requirement for superadobe walls.

Mogolla Serpentina

Overall, samples of *Serpentina* were in compliance with the minimum compressive requirements. As added cement by volume increases, compressive strength is also expected to increase. However, values from the group with 10% added cement averaged a smaller psi than those in the 7% group. The 10% group also showed a higher standard deviation. In Figure 5, a graph comparing the averages of each sample group is shown. In the graph, although the average is above the minimum requirement, the variability of samples from the 10% cement group show a higher frequency of compressive strength below the accepted minimum. This variability may be due to human errors during the manufacturing process.

Table 1. Summary of results of *Mogolla Serpentina* samples.

<i>Mogolla Serpentina</i> samples					
7% added cement		10% added cement		13% added cement	
Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)	Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)	Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)
S7%1	399	S10%1	695	S13%1	606
S7%2	517	S10%2	564	S13%2	519
S7%3	366	S10%3	322	S13%3	455
S7%4	339	S10%4	147	S13%4	477
S7%5	368	S10%5	199	S13%5	490
S7%6	419	S10%6	284	S13%6	443
S7%7	373	S10%7	320	S13%7	457
S7%8	311	S10%8	334	S13%8	435
S7%9	327	S10%9	331	S13%9	557
S7%10	295	S10%10	358	S13%10	559
Average (psi)	371	Average (psi)	355	Average (psi)	500
Standard Deviation	64	Standard Deviation	162	Standard Deviation	58

Figure 5: Graph comparing average compressive strength of each *mogolla Serpentina* sample group.

Mogolla Caliza

Caliza samples were found to consistently surpass the minimum required compressive strength. The average of the sample groups also increased in proportion to added cement amounts. The standard

deviation of the 10% sample group was found to be the largest of all groups. This may point to human error during the manufacturing process. However, as seen in Figure 6, the values were found to comfortably surpass the minimum psi requirement.

Table 2. Summary of results of *Mogolla Caiza* samples.

<i>Mogolla Caliza</i> samples					
7% added cement		10% added cement		13% added cement	
Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)	Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)	Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)
Ca7%1	690	Ca10%1	1067	Ca13%1	1409
Ca7%2	717	Ca10%2	915	Ca13%2	1484
Ca7%3	605	Ca10%3	920	Ca13%3	1195
Ca7%4	508	Ca10%4	672	Ca13%4	1239
Ca7%5	646	Ca10%5	862	Ca13%5	1307
Ca7%6	547	Ca10%6	449	Ca13%6	1288
Ca7%7	472	Ca10%7	580	Ca13%7	1092
Ca7%8	504	Ca10%8	692	Ca13%8	1096
Ca7%9	475	Ca10%9	726	Ca13%9	1159
Ca7%10	419	Ca10%10	769	Ca13%10	948
Average (psi)	558	Average (psi)	765	Average (psi)	1222
Standard Deviation	101	Standard Deviation	182	Standard Deviation	159

Figure 6: Graph comparing average compressive strength of each *mogolla Serpentina* sample group.

Mogolla Caliza with clayey soil

Sample groups corresponding to this soil mix were the most difficult to manufacture due to the nature of the clayey soil. The clayey soil tends to clump together and must therefore be broken down thoroughly to be mixed appropriately with the *mogolla*. Sample groups for this soil mix resulted in the smallest average compressive strength of all groups. As with other soil mixes, 10% added cement group accounted for the largest standard deviation of the three sample groups, while 13% added cement group averaged highest of all the sample groups (Figure 7).

Table 3. Summary of results of *Mogolla Caliza* with clayey soil samples.

<i>Mogolla Caliza with clayey soil samples</i>					
7% added cement		10% added cement		13% added cement	
Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)	Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)	Sample ID	Compressive strength (psi)
CaB7%1	424	CaB10%1	590	CaB13%1	492
CaB7%2	362	CaB10%2	556	CaB13%2	538
CaB7%3	351	CaB10%3	591	CaB13%3	573
CaB7%4	344	CaB10%4	368	CaB13%4	382
CaB7%5	356	CaB10%5	407	CaB13%5	471
CaB7%6	305	CaB10%6	336	CaB13%6	399
CaB7%7	279	CaB10%7	293	CaB13%7	402
CaB7%8	120	CaB10%8	433	CaB13%8	412
CaB7%9	390	CaB10%9	314	CaB13%9	416
CaB7%10	282	CaB10%10	224	CaB13%10	408
Average	321	Average	411	Average	449
Standard Deviation	84	Standard Deviation	130	Standard Deviation	66

Figure 7: Graph comparing average compressive strength of each *mogolla Serpentina* sample group.

CONCLUSIONS

This study explored several superadobe mixes used in Puerto Rico, and their suitability to meet 2018 IRC code requirement standards. Superadobe mixes were tested for compliance with compressive strength, to identify which mixes should be studied further for compliance with other code requirements. Soil mixes were sourced from two local quarries and tested with varying amounts of added cement (7%, 10% and 13%), these were: *Mogolla Serpentina*, *Mogolla Caliza* and *Mogolla Caliza* with 20% of clayey soil added by volume. Average compressive strength for all sample groups met the minimum requirement. However, all sample groups experienced high standard deviation and variance. This points to human errors during the elaboration process which were most likely variations in moisture content and non-uniform mixing and tamping.

Of all mixes, sample groups with 10% cement showed the most variance between compressive strength. This may indicate that mixes with 10% are more sensitive to variations in mix preparation. On the other hand, sample groups with 13% added cement surpassed the minimum requirement for all soil mixes. This is consistent with the proportional relationship between added cement and compressive strength. However, these sample groups may be only favorable in specific structural elements of earthen structures. In the case of superadobe, these sample mixes could be employed in the case of foundations or openings, where higher psi is required.

The sample groups with the highest compressive strength corresponded to the *Mogolla Caliza* soil mix. These sample groups comfortably surpassed the minimum compressive strength requirement. Given these results, it is recommended that further studies be performed to corroborate compliance of this superadobe mix with other code requirements such as modulus of rupture. Other superadobe mixes were also found to meet the minimum requirement; however, their variance can often fall beneath the 300 psi requirement. This indicates that though these mixes have the capacity to meet this requirement, a strict quality control protocol must be employed when doing so to minimize variance during the process. The quality control should be focused on maintaining proper moisture levels in the mix, ensuring uniform mixing of particle sizes, and guaranteeing proper tamping. The methodology and findings here described can also be employed for other earthen construction techniques such as adobe, rammed earth and cob.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.